

Development and characterization of Ag₂O-doped ZnLB glasses and biological assessment of Ag₂O-ZnLB-hydroxyapatite composites

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Abstract

This work aims to report the preparation, physico-chemical characterization, antibacterial activity and biocompatibility testing of novel Ag-containing ZnO-Li₂O-B₂O₃-hydroxyapatite composites, which are intended to be applied in bone tissue regenerative applications.

Silver oxide (0.5, 1, 2 and 4 mol%) doped ZnO-Li₂O-B₂O₃ (Ag₂O-ZLB) glasses were prepared by conventional quenching techniques. The newly developed glasses were characterized by X-ray diffraction, Raman and Fourier transforms infrared spectroscopy, and Scanning electron microscopy. Furthermore, glass-ceramic composites (Ag₂O-ZnLB-hydroxyapatite composites) were obtained by the mixture of 2.5wt% of each silver glass with 97.5wt% of hydroxyapatite, and thoroughly characterized. The initial bacteria adhesion was evaluated using *E. coli*, whereas the biocompatibility profile of these materials was assessed following the establishment of MG63 osteoblast-like cell cultures, for 7 days. All the assayed compositions revealed a significant antibacterial activity against *E.coli*, at early culture time points. Moreover, osteoblastic cells revealed an adequate adhesion to all the assayed Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA compositions and following, an active proliferation was established over seeded materials, throughout the culture period. No signs of cytotoxicity were attained by the assessment of cell morphology, viability and proliferation. Furthermore, the composites containing a higher amount of silver (2 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA and 4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA) allowed an increased cell proliferation, in comparison to control.

Keywords: Silver doped glasses; Glass-ceramic composite; Physical properties; Biological evaluation; *In vitro* testing

1. Introduction

In bone tissue engineering strategies, the development of new biomaterials has been an area of active research ¹. Currently, regenerative approaches may reach hand from a diverse range of ceramic-based materials that have been employed to promote osseointegration or bone tissue regeneration, relying on their adequate biological, mechanical and physicochemical properties, and ability to bond with mineralized tissues ^{2; 3}.

To more closely mimic the structure, composition and activity of the biological apatite, several attempts have been assayed within the development of biomaterials for bone tissue regeneration, including the development of glass-ceramic composites ⁴. The addition of biological active glasses to synthetic hydroxyapatite has been shown to improve both mechanical and biological properties of the composite material ^{5; 6; 7; 8; 9}. Glass-ceramic composites derive their improved strength from a crystal structure of fine interlocking acicular crystals, that display an enhanced mechanical strength compared to that of the base materials alone ¹⁰. Moreover, glasses can be used as a source of dopant ions which may be able to, on one way, modulate the microstructure, crystallinity and physicochemical properties of hydroxyapatite, and on the other way, be timely released into the microenvironment, in order to modulate the biological response in terms of promoting bone tissue formation ^{11; 12; 13}. In this respect, the addition of wide range of metal or non-metal oxides to glasses' composition has been shown to improve the biological response to osteoblasts – both in which regards to proliferation and differentiation events – and improve the bone-bonding ability of developed materials ^{14; 15; 16}. Accordingly, the

clinical application of glass-ceramic composites has been established and proven to be successful in a wide range of orthopaedic and dental interventions ^{17; 18; 19}.

Moreover, within the clinical scenario, the adequacy of use of grafting materials may be narrowed by the establishment of biomaterial-related infections ²⁰. Even though infection is not a common reason for grafting failure, it accounts for an enormous medical cost, increase in morbidity and a decrease in patient satisfaction ²⁰. Lately, in order to reduce the incidence of implant-associated infections, the biomaterial impregnation or loading with antimicrobial agents, such as antibiotics, quaternary ammonium compounds, iodine or silver (Ag) ions, has been established ^{21; 22; 23; 24}. In fact, Ag ionic species have been widely used due to their bactericidal ability. Ag binds to bacterial DNA inducing its denaturation and ability to replicate, and interacts with proteic thiol groups, impairing the functional activity of proteins ²⁵. Moreover, silver cations are microcidal at low concentrations – generally without adverse effects for human tissues – and the development of bacterial resistance to silver, unlike to antibiotics, has been rare and sporadic ^{26; 27}. Silver-loaded bioceramics and composites have been developed for bone tissue engineering applications aiming to take advantage of the antibacterial properties of silver, in conjugation with an improved biological response induced by the controlled release of specific compounds ^{28; 29; 30}.

In this way, this work aims to report the preparation and characterization of novel Ag₂O (0.5-4 mol%) doped ZnO-Li₂O-B₂O₃ (Ag₂O-ZnLB) host glasses. Furthermore, the preparation, characterization and biological assessment – in terms of both antibacterial and osteoblastic activity – of glass-ceramic composites, resulting from the mixture of 2.5 wt%

glasses with pure phase synthetic hydroxyapatite (Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA), has also been conducted.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Fabrication of Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses

Silver oxide (0.5-4 mol %) doped ZnO-Li₂O-B₂O₃ (Ag₂O-ZnLB) host glasses with the following chemical compositions (mol %), have been prepared:

Glasses were obtained by melting the chemical mixture of analytical grade ZnO, Li₂CO₃, B₂O₃ and Ag₂O raw chemicals (Sigma Aldrich - 99.99% purity), in crucibles, for about an hour. The quenching technique was applied, and the melting process was conducted in an electrical furnace, at a temperature of 1000 °C. For convenience, the above glasses have been labelled as 0.5Ag, 1Ag, 2Ag and 4Ag.

The attained glasses presented a good transparency and an irregular circular design, with around 2.0 - 3.0 cm in diameter, and a thickness of about 0.33 - 0.38 cm. Following, they were annealed at 200°C, for an hour, in order to remove thermal strains, previously to being crushed and sieved to granules ($\leq 75 \mu\text{m}$), for further characterization.

2.2. Preparation of the Hydroxyapatite (HA) and (Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA) composites

Hydroxyapatite, with the chemical composition of Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂, has been prepared in accordance with the following chemical equation:

In brief, analytical grade calcium hydroxide, Ca(OH)₂ and ortho phosphoric acid, H₃PO₄, have been independently mixed with deionised water and subsequently, Ca(OH)₂ has been slowly transferred into H₃PO₄, during 4 hours, in constant mixing conditions (100 rpm) and with maintenance of the pH at 10.50. After 24 hours, the material was filtered to remove the excess of water and dried, at 60°C, for approximately 48 hours. The dried product was finally crushed and sieved to granules ($\leq 75 \mu\text{m}$).

Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites were obtained by mixing 2.5wt% of each glass (0.5Ag, 1Ag, 2Ag and 4Ag) with 97.5wt% of HA, in deionised water, with tubular mixing to assure homogeneity. The obtained composites were dried at 60°C, for 24 hours, and sieved to less than 75 μm . Composite disks were prepared by isostatic pressure at 200 MPa and sintered at 1300°C, for 1 hour. Composites were designated, respectively, as 0.5Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, 1Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, 2Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, and 4Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, according to the addition of either 0.5Ag, 1Ag, 2Ag or 4Ag glasses. Prior to further characterization, sample discs were cleaned, degreased and sterilized in a steam autoclave.

2. 3. Materials Characterization

Glass density was measured using ethyl glycol as an immersion liquid, by Archimedes' principle, on a Mettler Toledo balance. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was

performed on powder samples of 0.5 Ag, 1Ag, 2Ag and 4Ag glass samples as well as on 0.5Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, 1Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, 2Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, and 4Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites, by using Siemens D 5000 diffractometer, with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418\text{\AA}$). The scans were made in the range of 25-40° (2 θ), with a step size of 0.02° and a count time of 2 sec/step.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the range of 400-4000cm⁻¹, at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, on a Jasco FT/IR – 460 PLUS spectrophotometer. The spectrum was recorded by using KBr pellets containing approximately 95% of KBr and 5% of silver oxide glass sample, in 250mg of a pellet. Before recording the spectra, the samples were dried in a Buchi Glass Oven- B-585, at 120°C, for 1 hour.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and colour coded X-ray mapping were performed in a FEI Quanta 400 FEG ESEM / EDAX Genesis X4M, a high-resolution environmental Scanning Electron Microscope with X-ray microanalysis and backscattered electron diffraction pattern analysis. Both SEM images and mappings were obtained in a high vacuum mode and with an acceleration of 500kV. In order to avoid superficial charge accumulation, the samples were covered with a carbon film. X-ray maps were acquired in regions of 500x400 μm , for a period of 15 minutes.

The unpolarized micro-sampling Raman spectra of the glasses were recorded in the backscattering geometry, at room temperature, by using an Olympus BH2 UMA microscope and a x50 lens. The 514.53 nm polarized line of Ar⁺ laser was used for excitation, with an incident power of about 150 mW impinging the sample. The scattered

light was analysed using a T64000 Jobin-Yvon spectrometer operating in the triple subtractive mode and equipped with a LN2 cooled CCD. Identical conditions were kept constant for all measurements. The spectral slit width was about 1.5 cm^{-1} and the spatial resolution on the sample was about $1 \mu\text{m}$.

2.4. *Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites antibacterial activity to Escherichia coli*

The *E. coli* strain was isolated from the biofilm on the surface of an infected prosthesis from patients with prosthetic joint infection. Strain characterization was made by VITEK 2 automated system (bioMérieux). *E. coli* strain was incubated in Tryptic soy broth - TSB, at 37°C in an orbital shaking incubator at 150 rpm, in order to obtain an exponential growth phase culture. Following, cells were harvested by centrifugation and re-suspended in TSB for adhesion assays. The optical density (670nm) of the culture was adjusted to 1×10^8 bacteria/mL and used in the adhesion assays.

Sterilized hydroxyapatite and 0.5-4Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composite discs were placed in a microplate for bacterial growth, at 37°C , in an orbital shaking incubator at 150 rpm, during 2 hours, and were washed three times with TSB. Following, 1 mL of the bacterial suspension was added to each well, and the plate was incubated in the previously described conditions, for to 2 hours. Following, seeded materials were stained with the Live/Dead BacLight Bacterial Viability Kit L-7007 (Molecular Probes, Inc., Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's procedure, before fluorescent microscopy examination in an ApoTome fluorescence microscope (Zeiss®). From each sample, twenty to thirty randomly areas of triplicate samples were taken. To estimate the number of adhered bacteria, green cells were considered to be viable and red cells and yellow cells were considered to be dead. All

experiments were performed four times. From the combined data, average and standard deviation were calculated, and results were expressed as percentage of adhered dead cells per sample. Analysis of the results was carried out with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

2.5. Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites biological response to MG63 osteoblast-like cells

MG63 cells, human osteosarcoma-derived osteoblastic cells, were cultured in α -Minimal Essential Medium (α -MEM), supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum, ascorbic acid ($50 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{ml}^{-1}$), penicillin-streptomycin ($100 \text{ IU}\cdot\text{ml}^{-1}$ and $100 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{ml}^{-1}$, respectively) and fungizone ($2.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{ml}^{-1}$), at 37°C , in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO_2 in air. For sub-culturing, adherent cells were enzymatically released (5 minutes at 37°C - 0.05% trypsin - 0.25% EDTA) and re-suspended in complete culture medium for reseeding. Cells were cultured at a density of $2 \times 10^4 \text{ cells}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, for 7 days, on the surface of the culture plate (control), hydroxyapatite, and over 0.5Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, 1Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, 2Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA, and 4Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composite discs, that had been previously immersed in complete culture medium for 1h.

Seeded material samples were evaluated throughout the incubation time for cell viability/proliferation (MTT assay) and were observed by confocal laser scanning microscopy.

The MTT assay was conducted, in every experimental conditions, at days 1, 2, 5 and 7. Briefly, cultures were incubated with 0.5mg/ml of MTT, during 4 hours. The medium was following decanted, formazan crystals dissolved and the absorbance measured at 600nm in a spectrophotometer (Biotek Synergy II). Results were expressed as

absorbance per square centimetre (A/cm^2). Analysis of the results was carried out with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

For confocal microscopy observation, cells grown over the samples were fixed, at selected timepoint, in 3.7% methanol-free formaldehyde and permeabilized with 0.1% Triton. Cell cytoskeleton filamentous actin (F-actin) was visualized by treating the fixed cells with Alexa Fluor® 488-conjugated phalloidin dye (1:100 in PBS, 20 minutes), after initial incubation with bovine serum albumin (10 mg.ml^{-1} in PBS, 1 hour), in order to block non-specific interactions. Cells were counterstained with propidium iodide (10 mg.ml^{-1} , 10 minutes) for cell nuclei labelling. Labelled cultures were mounted in Vectashield® and examined with a Leica SP2 AOBS (Leica Microsystems®) microscopy.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical parameters of Ag_2O -ZnLB glasses

In order to understand how the features of the host glass matrices are affected by the composition of Ag_2O in the sample, some physical properties of the glasses were computed. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical properties of Ag_2O (0.5-4.0 mol%) doped ZnLB glasses

Glasses	Density (d) (g.cm^{-3})	Average Molecular weight (\bar{M}) (g/mol)	Molar Volume (V_m) ($\text{cm}^3.\text{mol}^{-1}$)	Crystal Volume (V_c) ($\text{cm}^3.\text{mol}^{-1}$)	Ag ion concentration N ($\times 10^{20}$ ions/ cm^3)

0.5 Ag	2.75	66.22	24.30	4.63	2..51
1Ag	2.82	66.07	23.78	4.56	5.01
2Ag	2.92	68.77	23.51	4.44	10.0
4 Ag	3.08	72.17	23.39	4.20	20.0

The density of a glass is a powerful tool to examine the structural compactness of a glass network. It was observed that by modifying the proportion of silver oxide in the glass samples, a variation of other physical properties, such as density and molar volume, were attained. The addition of a high atomic mass element to the network, such as silver oxide (231.74), is expected to result in an increase of the density. In the other hand, the molar volume decreases with an increasing amount of silver oxide. The variation of molar volume can be explained by the equation:

$$V_m = \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

where M stands for the average molecular weight of the oxide glass, and ρ for density of the glass. Eq. 2 shows an inverse correlation between density and the molar volume.

Figure 1: Comparison between molar volume (V_m) of the glasses and crystalline phase of the raw materials (V_c)

In Figure 1, it is plotted the molar volume of the glasses (V_m), and the sum of the volumes of the reactants in their crystalline phase (V_c). As one can observe, for all compositions, V_m is greater than the sum of the volumes of the crystalline phases of the reactants. Therefore, the prepared glasses present an excess of structural volume. Furthermore, silver oxide will break the bonds of the glass network by the creation of non-bridging oxygens, resulting in an expansion of the volume. With increasing concentration of silver oxide the difference between V_c and V_m decreases, which suggests a better packing of silver ions in the network^{31; 32}. In fact, there is a theoretical model for borate glasses doped with metal oxides^{33; 34}. Krogh-Moe model states that the addition of a metal oxide to a borate glass causes an increase of the number of four-coordinated boron's. This

effect can be represented by the equilibrium between the tetrahedral and triangular units in the matrix ³⁵:

For instance, in a $M_2O-2B_2O_3$ glass, 45% of the boron is four-coordinated ³⁶. Thus, the introduction of a metal oxide in the B_2O_3 matrix changes the structural network of the glass. However, the metal ion does not participate in the network rearrangement ^{31; 33; 34}. They coordinate to the negatively charged BO_4 units and their effect on the intermediate-range structure of the glass depends on their size and degree of covalence. Therefore, different ions do not produce the same effects in the glass network. These differences will imply a variation of the density number, accordingly to the added metal ion. It is clear that the variation of the density number results in the variation of the molar volume, as verified in Eq.2 ³³.

The density d and average molecular weight \bar{M} were also used to evaluate the concentration of silver ions ($N \times 10^{20}$ ions/cm³) with the following equation. Data is presented in Table 1.

$$N_{Ag^+} (cm^{-3}) = \frac{\frac{n(Ag^+)}{n_t} \times N_A \times \rho_g}{M} \quad (4)$$

Where $n(Ag^+)$ is the number of moles of silver ions in the batch, n_t the total number of moles in the glass, N_A the Avogadro's number, ρ_g the density of the glass and M its average molecular weight.

3.2. X-ray diffraction of Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses

The XRD patterns of the 0.5-4Ag doped Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses reveal the amorphous nature of the glass samples.

3.3. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and Raman Studies of the Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses

The FTIR spectra, in the range 4000-400 cm⁻¹, of the Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses system with different contents of silver oxide are presented in Figure 2. All the samples analysed yielded very similar results.

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of Ag₂O (0.5-4mol%) doped ZnLB glasses.

The spectra profiles showed a broad absorption band at around 3000-3500 cm⁻¹ and 1650 cm⁻¹ which are mainly due to the stretching and bending of the hydroxyl or water groups present in the glass matrix^{37; 38}. The KBr used to make the pallets is very hygroscopic; therefore it is normal to observe these bands in the spectra. The band in the range 2358-2315 cm⁻¹ is the typical signature of atmospheric carbon dioxide³⁹. It is also observed a band at around 2932, which can be assigned to hydrogen bonding⁴⁰. The

spectra containing a number of strong, extensively convoluted bands are characteristic of the FTIR spectra from all borate glasses. So, in order to better understand the bands assignments', a band deconvolution was performed and shown in Figure 3. Table 2 presents the wave numbers for the different bands observed in the spectra.

Figure 3: Deconvolution FTIR bands for 1Ag₂O- ZnLB glass

Table 2: Assignments and positions for the different FTIR bands present in the Ag₂O (0.5- 4 mol%) doped ZnLB glasses

Literature data (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment	ZnLB Glasses				
			0.5% Ag ₂ O	1% Ag ₂ O	2% Ag ₂ O	4% Ag ₂ O
466 ⁴¹	Specific vibrations of Zn—O bonds in ZnO ₄ units	Position	460	472	472	461
496 ⁴³	Zn-O stretching band	Position	480	-	489	491
560 ⁴⁴	Ag—O vibrations	Position	560	560	565	561
		Area	-	0.001	0.002	0.003

690 ⁴¹	B—O—B angle bending vibrations from pentaborate groups	Position	686	686	683	684
870 ⁴¹	Stretching vibrations of B—O bonds in BO ₄ units from tri-, tetra- and pentaborate groups	Position	-	852	875	878
963 ⁴¹	B—O stretching vibrations of BO ₄ units in diborate groups	Position	909	942	965	964
1098 ⁴¹	B—O stretching vibrations of BO ₄ units in pentaborate groups	Position	1055	1085	1110	1107
1225 ⁴¹	B—O stretching vibrations of BO ₃ units in orthoborate groups	Position	1250	1244	1254	1253
1328 ⁴¹	B—O stretching vibrations of BO ₃ units in pyroborate groups	Position	1381	1373	1356	1338
1407 ⁴¹	B—O stretching vibrations of BO ₃ units in chain and ring type metaborate groups	Position	1479	1471	1454	1443
1647-1671 ³⁸	Bending modes of OH groups	Position	1603	1612	1614	1626
2345 ³⁹	C=O valence vibration	Position	2349	2356	2341	2348
2932 ⁴⁰	Hydrogen bonding	Position	2925	2921	2920	2920
3600-3300 ³⁷	O-H stretching vibration	Position	3479	3444	3448	3452

The arrangement of the different borate groups present in the sample is in agreement with the literature^{31; 41}. The presence of metal oxygen bond may be confirmed by the appearance of bands in the spectra of all the doped glasses in the region below 500 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(\text{Zn-O})$ ^{42; 43}. In fact, this region is associated to the vibration of cations in the network^{44; 45}. For the silver ion, it was also measured the area of the Gaussian curves. This parameter is expected to provide information about the concentration of Ag_2O in the samples. With an increasing amount of silver in the sample, the area under the curve also increases. Thus, we may assume that silver is being properly distributed within the glass matrix.

Figure 4: Raman spectra of Ag_2O (0.5-4mol%) doped ZnLB glasses

Raman analysis was also performed in the prepared glasses. In Figure 4, it is clearly visible a band corresponding to the symmetric breathing vibrations of boroxol rings⁴⁶, as reported on Table 3.

Table 3: Raman assignments for the 1 Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Assignment
437 ⁴⁷	Zn-O vibrations
765 ⁴⁶	Symmetric breathing vibrations of six-member rings with one or two BØ ₃ triangles replaced by BØ ₄ tetrahedra
796 ⁴⁶	
1110 ⁴⁶	Diborate groups
1275 ⁴⁶	Pyroborate units
1360 ⁴⁶	BØ ₂ O ⁻ triangles linked to BØ ₄ units
1460 ⁴⁶	BØ ₂ O ⁻ triangles linked to other borate triangular units

With increasing amounts of silver oxide, it is observed a shift of this band to the left. With a higher amount of silver oxide it is also observed that the intensity of boroxol rings band decreases. This may suggest that the addition of silver oxide promotes the formation of BO₃ and BO₄ units. At around 491 cm⁻¹ it is observed a weak band which may correspond to the vibration of Zn-O bonds⁴⁷.

3.4. X- ray mapping of Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses

X-ray mapping has become a fundamental tool in materials science. In order to analyse the distribution of silver in the sample, X-ray maps were performed and the results for 2Ag₂O-ZnLB and 4Ag₂O-ZnLB samples are showed in Figure 5. The small dots present

in the analysis of the 2Ag₂O-ZnLB glass sample confirm the presence of Silver in the glass matrix (Figure 5, Left). On the other hand, regarding the analysis of the 4Ag₂O-ZnLB glass samples, a more homogeneously distribution of Ag was verified (Figure 5, Right)

Figure 5: Color coded X-Ray map for 2% Ag₂O- ZnLB glass (Left) and 4% of Ag₂O-ZnLB glass (Right). The dots indicate in the circle the presence of silver in the glass host

3.5. XRD and Morphological analysis of Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites

XRD spectra for all the prepared composites (0.5- 4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA) and a sample of pure HA were also analyzed in order to compare the changes induced by the glass. In all the composites, hydroxyapatite and β , α – TCP were the chemical phases observed (data not shown).

SEM micrographs of the Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA samples revealed a similar structure for the samples prepared with different types of Ag₂O-ZnLB glasses. In Figure 6, the SEM micrograph of the 1% Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA sample is presented.

Figure 6: SEM picture (5000x) of 1% Ag₂O - ZnLB-HA composite

The image shows a well-defined structure being composed by HA and Ag₂O doped ZnLB glass grains. This surface is continuous and crack-free, suggesting a strong bonding between the grains. Furthermore, the glass compositions do not interfere with grain size of the composite. All composites were prepared with 2.5wt% glass addition and were sintered at the same temperature. Although the Ag composition had effects on antibacterial properties, it did not change the chemical phases present on the composites. Attributable to the high similarity between samples regardless the silver content, only one image of the composites microstructure is shown.

3.6. *In vitro* antibacterial activity of Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites

The adhesion behaviour of *E. coli* to developed materials was assessed at two hours of culture, by a life/dead fluorescent assay and image data analysis. Bacterial adhesion was assessed through a dynamic adhesion method to simulate the most conceivable bone microenvironment conditions. The results obtained revealed that a significantly higher percentage of adhered dead cells were found in seeded 0.5-4Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites, comparing to control (hydroxyapatite). Representative images and quantitative data are shown in Figure 7. *E. coli* is a common Gram-negative microorganism, usually present in bone-related infections and /or prosthetic joint infections. The behaviour of bacterial adhesion to implanted material's surfaces is one of the most important concerns in biofilm formation and therefore in the control of acute and chronic bone-related infections. Bacterial adhesion to engineered surfaces is mediated by several factors, including electrostatic attraction and physical forces, nevertheless the interrelationship among media, chemical and physical surface proprieties also seem to be critical to bacterial adhesion ⁴⁸;
⁴⁹. The higher percentage of dead attached bacterial cells to the 0.5-4Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA

composites suggests that the Ag release, even in small amounts, could be responsible for the induction of the adhered bacterial death. In accordance, several Ag-containing materials for bone tissue application have been shown to report a significant antibacterial activity ⁵⁰; 51; 52; 53 .

Figure 7: Representative microscopic appearance of HA (A) and 4 Ag2O-ZnLB-HA (B) composite samples, seeded with *E. coli* for 2 hours, following staining for life/dead assay. Green cells were considered to be viable, while red and yellow cells were considered to be dead. (C) Percentage of adhered dead *E. coli*, cultured for 2 hours, on the surface of HA and 0.5-4 Ag2O-ZnLB-HA composites. *Significant different from control.

It is generally accepted that the antibacterial mechanism of action of Ag ions is very complex and unclear, but some studies suggested that Ag ions seem to bind to the bacterial cell out-layer causing modifications in membrane permeability, with consequent release of lipopolysaccharide and membrane proteins into the extracellular environment⁵⁴. Ag ions also seem to interact with intracellular structures, as nucleic acids and proteins in cytoplasm and ribosomes, inhibiting translation and replication mechanisms with consequently bacterial death^{25; 54}.

3.7. *In vitro* biological evaluation of Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites

MG63 human osteoblast-like cells were cultured on the surface of 0.5-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites, HA samples, and on the surface of the culture plate, for 7 days. The biological assessment of the seeded materials was conducted by the MTT assay and confocal laser scanning microscopy, following staining for F-actin cytoskeleton and nucleus counterstaining.

Figure 8: Cell viability/proliferation of MG63 osteoblastic cells cultured for 7 days on the culture plate (control), and on the surface of HA and 0.5-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites. *Significant different from control.

Results regarding cell viability/proliferation (MTT assay) of control cultures, seeded HA and 0.5-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites are shown in Figure 8. Cells growing on the material samples presented a high proliferation rate throughout the 7-day period of culture. At early incubation times (1 day), values of MTT reduction were similar in control cultures and seeded material samples, suggesting that identical number of cells attached to the standard tissue culture plate and the assayed materials. Subsequently, cells growing in the surface of 0.5-1 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites presented an active proliferation, similar to control and hydroxyapatite, while composites containing higher amounts of silver (2-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA) revealed a significant increased cell proliferation.

Figure 9: Confocal laser scanning microscopy appearance of control (a), HA (b), 0.5 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA (c), 1 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA (d), 2 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA (e) and 4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA (f) composite samples, cultured with MG63 cells, for 5 days. Scale bar represents 300 μm.

The time-course behaviour of seeded materials was also addressed by confocal laser scanning microscopy (Figure 9). Low magnification images revealed that, at day 2 of culture, Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites were densely colonised with MG63 cells, reporting areas of high cell density (data not shown). Qualitatively, an increased cell density could be observed on cultures established over 2 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA and 4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA samples, compared to the remaining experimental conditions that broadly reveal a similar number of adhered cells. Following, cells proliferated actively throughout the culture time and, at day 5 (Figure 8), a densely organized cell layer could be attained over control, seeded HA and seeded 0.5-1 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites. An increased proliferation was achieved in 2 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA and 4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites' surface, as shown by the establishment of cell multilayers.

The assessment of seeded cell morphology, as addressed by confocal laser scanning microscopy, was conducted at day 2 of culture, with high magnification (data not shown). Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites allowed, at every assayed composition (0.5-4 Ag₂O), the normal morphological display of MG63 osteoblastic cells. Comparing to seeded HA and control, a similar degree of cytoplasmic spreading, the setting up of prominent nucleus and nucleoli, as well as the establishment of numerous filipodia - that allowed the attainment of extensive intercellular contacts - were verified.

The acquisition of characteristic cellular morphology following adhesion is in agreement with the adequate reorganization of the cytoskeleton during the first 12-24 hours of the established cultures, and it is amply verified within the assayed composites' surface. The cytoskeleton is a dynamic structure that plays an important role both in the trafficking of intracellular mediators and in intracellular-extracellular signalling pathways,

determining many cellular events, including the ability to modulate gene expression⁵⁵. This is a matter of particular relevance, as the early cytoskeleton re-organization events during the phases of cell attachment/adhesion, might govern the long term cellular function on the surface of the assayed substrate, i.e. the quality of initial adhesion can influence cell morphology, and the capacity for cell proliferation and differentiation over the seeded substrate^{56; 57}. Changes in cytoskeleton reorganization during the adhesion phase to a biomaterials' surface have been critically assayed in the evaluation of the *in vitro* biological response to biomaterials, since these have been correlated with downstream cytotoxic events⁵⁵.

These results seem to be in accordance with recent literature reports, in which the cytotoxicity and biocompatibility of silver-containing or silver coated-materials for bone tissue application have been addressed^{58; 59; 60}. Silver coated stainless steel was shown not to cause any cell-cycle delay or morphological changes in seeded osteoblast-like cells. Further, a proper osteoblastic activity, both in terms of proliferation and differentiation were verified, particularly at longer culture times⁵⁹. Also, the addition of a low quantity of silver, in the 5-10 mg range, was shown not to be cytotoxic and to induce the alkaline phosphatase activity – a marker of the osteoblastic differentiation – in the HOS-58 human osteosarcoma-derived cell line⁵⁸. In accordance, low concentrations of silver (in the range of 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} M) seemed to enhance the osteoinductive properties of demineralized bone matrix following intramuscular implantation in a rat, while higher concentrations (10^{-5} M) failed to do so⁶⁰. Proposed mechanisms by which low concentration of Ag seem to enhance the biological function of osteoblastic cells remain to be depicted and are currently broadly unclear. These may be associated with a direct effect of Ag over cellular metabolic

functions, or even by a modification of the surface characteristics of the assayed Ag-containing biomaterials, that converge to broaden the enhancement of the biological response^{58; 59; 60; 61}.

In the present work, the composites contained a reduced amount of silver, not detected by the conducted elemental analysis, and revealed a significant antibacterial activity and an improved osteoblastic behaviour, comparing to hydroxyapatite. Nonetheless, *in vivo*, several factors may influence the availability of Ag. The surface of the implanted materials could be conditioned by the formation of a protein-rich apatite layer, which is usually verified in contact with biological fluids, that can blight the Ag release and its availability⁶². Further, released Ag could be adsorbed by albumin and precipitate into insoluble silver chloride, thus further reducing the free form of Ag with biological activity⁶³. Accordingly, further studies should be conducted in order to disclose and detail the *in vivo* effectiveness of the 0.5-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites, especially in terms of the antimicrobial activity and the capacity to enhance the bone regeneration process.

4. Conclusions

A set of different silver oxide (0.5-4 mol%)-doped ZnLB host glasses was prepared, characterized and mixed with HA to produce 0.5-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites. Regarding the developed glasses, it was observed that increasing the amount of silver oxide resulted in a decrease in the molar volume and an increase in the density. Moreover, the structure of the attained glasses was amorphous with the formation of metallic silver clusters, as revealed by SEM analysis and X-ray mappings.

Developed composites were further characterized regarding antibacterial and osteoblastic activity. 0.5-4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites reported an increased antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, comparing to control. In addition, assayed materials allowed for adequate cell adhesion and proliferation. The 2 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA and 4 Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA compositions significantly induced cell proliferation, throughout the culture period. These results output a suitable biological behaviour of Ag₂O-ZnLB-HA composites, substantiating the prospective application of these materials in bone tissue regenerative applications.

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